

AN ALTERNATIVE APPROACH FOR DIFFERENTIAL EVOLUTION ALGORITHM

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Abstract

The differential evolution algorithm is an effective method for global numerical optimization that is straightforward to understand, easy to implement, reliable, and efficient. As one of the evolutionary algorithms, Differential Evolution addresses global optimization problems by iteratively refining candidate solutions through an evolutionary process. It serves as a heuristic technique for minimizing potentially nonlinear and non-differentiable continuous functions. Global minimization algorithms require efficient computational time, which motivates the use of parallel computational approaches. This new technique utilizes multiple independent parallel computing units that occasionally share the best solutions they have discovered. This study proposes an improved approach designed to minimize the number of function calls, thereby strengthening the method's efficiency in exploring the objective function's search space. The proposed parallelizing Differential Evolution algorithm has been tested on several of optimization problems, and it appears from the experimental results that the executing time of the proposed parallelizing Differential Evolution becomes faster compared with Classic Differential Evolution and the other previous modifications of Differential Evolution. Also, results indicate significant improvements in function evaluations and solution quality compared to existing methodologies, demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Global Optimization, Metaheuristics, Parallel Computing, Differential Evolution Algorithm.

1. INTRODUCTION

The assignment of locating the global minimum of a continuous and differentiable function

$f: S \rightarrow R, S \subset R^n$ is expressed as:

$$x^* = \arg \min_{x \in S} f(x) \quad (1)$$

Where the set S is defined as:

$$S = [a_1, b_1] \otimes [a_2, b_2] \otimes \dots \otimes [a_n, b_n]$$

The real-world problems can be modelled as global optimization problems, such as problems from physics [1–3], chemistry [4–6], economics [7, 8], medicine [9, 10], etc. Recently, different algorithms have been proposed to tackle the problem of Equation (1), such as simulated annealing methods [11–13], differential evolution (DE) methods [14], particle swarm optimization methods [15], ant colony optimization [16], genetic algorithms [17, 18], etc. The DE algorithm firstly generates a population of candidate solutions, which iteratively evolves through the crossover stage in order to determine the

global minimum of the objective function. The method has been applied across various research fields, including electromagnetics [19], energy consumption problems [20], job shop scheduling [21], and image segmentation [22]. Differential Evolution has evolved into a reliable and versatile optimization tool that is used easily. The initial publication on DE appeared as a technical report in 1995 (Storn and Price 1995). Since then, DE has demonstrated its effectiveness in competitions, such as the IEEE's International Contest on Evolutionary Optimization (ICEO) in 1996 and 1997, and in a wide range of real-world applications. DE's performance can be enhanced, and its methodology adapted to various optimization scenarios. It operates on a population of candidate solutions, referred to as individuals, and iteratively refines them toward the optimal solution. This algorithm makes minimal assumptions about the optimization problems, allowing for rapid exploration of large design spaces [23]. DE is considered one of the most versatile and robust population-based search algorithms, effectively handling multi-modal problems [24].

In this paper, a modified parallel DE presents an approach that requires fewer total evaluations to reach the optimum value, achieving convergence with minimal external iterations of the algorithm while successfully identifying the global minimum in several cases. The paper is structured as follows: the second section provides a literature review of DE and the proposed parallel DE, highlighting challenges related to parallelization and current strategies to address them. The third section describes the experimental test functions, while the fourth section discusses numerical experiments that optimize the parameters of the proposed parallel DE, along with the associated experimental results. Finally, the fifth section concludes the paper and offers suggestions for future research directions.

2. METHOD DESCRIPTION

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the base Differential Evolution algorithm, followed by an explanation of the proposed parallel Differential Evolution approach. Starts by generating a population of candidate solutions, followed by a stochastic search process through mutation which are iteratively refined through a crossover process to identify the global minimum of the objective function. The proposed method divides the processing into independent units, such as threads, allowing each to operate autonomously. Additionally, it outlines a communication framework for coordinating the various components in parallel processing and presents a termination technique specifically adapted for this parallel context.

The Base Differential Evolution Algorithm

Differential Evolution has demonstrated strong performance across a range of optimization problems in various scientific disciplines. As a stochastic population-based evolutionary method, DE operates using a population of candidate solutions and employs a stochastic search process through mutation, crossover, and selection operators, guiding the population toward improved solutions in the design space [24]. The foundational algorithm was first introduced by Storn [14] and has since undergone numerous modifications in various research studies. Examples include the compact differential evolution algorithm [25, 26], a self-adaptive DE

[27] that iteratively adjusts its parameters, and fuzzy logic modifications [28]. Additionally, a numerical study on various modifications of the DE method is presented by Kaelo et al. [29].

Description of the New Proposed Parallel DE

Implementing a parallel DE algorithm can produce weighty benefits in terms of computational efficiency and speedup, taking advantage of the power of parallel processing by executing several DE iterations concurrently, getting faster convergence, and minimizing execution time. Parallel implementations have been well beneficial for computationally intensive problems, and large-scale optimization scenarios consume the time for objective function evaluation. There are three challenges to confirming the efficient execution of parallelizing DE. The first vital challenge is the balance between exploring the search space and exploiting the better solutions, the second challenge is load balancing, which includes distributing the computational load uniformly across processing units to maximize efficiency, and the third one is communication overhead and synchronization between parallel processes. To overcome these challenges, it can be useful to use these approaches. first one, a master-slave architecture where a master process manages the overall execution and distributes subtasks to slave processes, second one, dividing the population into subgroups and processing them independently in parallel that can be combined with migration strategies, where individuals are exchanged between subgroups periodically to maintain diversity, third one, hybrid approaches that combine parallel DE with other optimization techniques [30].

Propagation Mechanism

In the proposed Parallel Differential Evolution (PDE) method, the algorithm uses a (1-to-1) propagation mechanism. Generally, a random island will send its best value to another randomly selected island. i.e., the best values of the islands are spread to the rest by replacing their worst values, this technique is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: (1-to-1) Propagation technique

The Termination Rule

In the base Differential Evolution algorithm, termination occurs after reaching a predefined number of iterations, which can sometimes result in premature halting before the global minimum is identified. In contrast, the proposed PDE method employs a termination criterion that evaluates the convergence of each island separately. Specifically, the difference is calculated as follows:

$$\delta_i^{(k)} = \left| f_{i,\min}^{(k)} - f_{i,\min}^{(k-1)} \right|, \quad (2)$$

In this equation, $f_{i,\min}^{(k)}$ represents the best function value found for island i iteration k . If $\delta_i^{(k)} \leq \epsilon$ for a specified number of iterations, then the population evolution for the island is terminated. Furthermore, in the proposed PDE method, if this condition holds for more than one island, the entire algorithm will terminate. The proposed PDE algorithm is listed below with the proposed terminating mechanism and mechanism for communication between the islands.

The steps of the proposed PDE algorithm	
1. INPUT:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The parameters NP, CR, F (b) The integer parameter N, which stands for the number of islands. (c) The integer parameter N_R, which represents the propagation rate. (d) The integer parameter N₁, which represents the number of islands that should Terminate in order to terminate the whole process.
2. OUTPUT:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The agent x_{best} with the lower function value f(x_{best}).
3. Initialize	all agents in S .
4.	Set iter = 1
5.	For i = 1, ..., N do in Parallel, Perform for every island i as follows:
i.	Set x as the agent i .
ii.	Pick randomly three agents , b, c .
iii.	Pick a random index R $\in \{1, \dots, n\}$.
iv.	Compute the trial vector y = $[y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n]$ with the following procedure
v.	For j = 1, ..., n do.
A.	Set r_i $\in [0,1]$ a random number.
B.	If r_j < CR or j = R then y_j = a_j + F × (b_j - c_j) else y_j = x_j .
vi.	If y $\in S$ AND f(y) ≤ f(x) then x = y .
vii.	EndFor .
6. EndFor	
7. If	iter mod N_R = 0 ,
	Apply the propagation scheme of Section (Propagation Mechanism) to the islands.
8. Set	iter = iter + 1
9. If	the termination rule of Section (The Termination Rule) is not valid, go to 5.
10. Apply	local search procedure to x_{best} . The local search procedure used in the proposed method is the BFGS variant of Powell [31].

In the proposed method, the parallel island model depicted in Figure 2, the population of agents is divided into N independent segments known as islands. This approach is a well-established variant in parallel genetic algorithms [32, 33]. For example, if there are 10 agents distributed across 2 islands, agents 1–5 will be assigned to island 1, while agents 6–10 will belong to island 2. Each island performs the differential evolution process independently.

Figure 2: flowchart of proposed Parallel Differential Evolution algorithm

3. TEST FUNCTIONS

The benchmark functions used in the experiments have a fairly complex structure, and some of them have a large number of dimensions that make them perfect for studying, testing and comparing the results with the modified differential evolution method of Tsoulos, I.G. [34].

Benchmark functions

To evaluate the effectiveness of the suggested parallel PDE method in locating the global minimum of functions, a set of test functions that are used here is selected [35, 36]. The selected functions are as follows:

- **BF1** function (Bohachevsky1) is defined as follows:

$$f(x) = x_1^2 + 2x_2^2 - \frac{3}{10} \cos(3\pi x_1) - \frac{4}{10} \cos(4\pi x_2) + \frac{7}{10}$$

With $x \in [-100, 100]^2$

- **BF2** function (Bohachevsky1) is defined as follows:

$$f(x) = x_1^2 + 2x_2^2 - \frac{3}{10} \cos(3\pi x_1) \cos(4\pi x_2) + \frac{3}{10}$$

With $x \in [-50, 50]^2$

- **BRANIN** function is given by:

$$f(x) = (x_2 - \frac{5.1}{4\pi^2} x_1^2 + \frac{5}{\pi} x_1 - 6)^2 + 10 \left(1 - \frac{1}{8\pi}\right) \cos(x_1) + 10$$

At range $-5 \leq x_1 \leq 10, 0 \leq x_2 \leq 15$.

- **CM** (Cosine Mixture) function

$$f(x) = 0.1 * \sum_{i=1}^n \cos(5\pi x_i) - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2$$

With $x \in [-1, 1]^n$

- **Camel back** function. Six Hump The function is given by:

$$f(x) = 4x_1^2 - 2.1x_1^4 + \frac{1}{3}x_1^6 + x_1x_2 - 4x_2^2 + 4x_2^4$$

At range $-5 \leq x_i \leq 5$.

- **Easom** function is given by:

$$f(x) = -\cos(x_1) \cos(x_2) e^{-((x_2-\pi)^2 + (x_1-\pi)^2)}$$

With $x \in [-100, 100]^2$

- **EXPONENTIAL** function. The function is given by the following:

$$f(x) = - \exp\left(-0.5 \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2\right),$$

At range $-1 \leq x_i \leq 1$.

In the experiments the function used with $n = 4$. And the corresponding function are denoted by EXP16.

- **Goldstein and Price function.** The function is given by the equation:

$$f(x) = [1 + (x_1 + x_2 + 1)^2 (19 - 14x_1 + 3x_1^2 - 14x_2 + 6x_1x_2 + 3x_2^2)] * [30 + (2x_1 - 3x_2)^2 (18 - 32x_1 + 12x_1^2 + 48x_2 - 36x_1x_2 + 27x_2^2)].$$

With $x \in [-2, 2]^2$

- **GRIEWANK** function. The function is given by the following:

$$f(x) = 1 + \frac{1}{200} \sum_{i=1}^2 x_i^2 - \prod_{i=1}^2 \frac{\cos(x_i)}{\sqrt{|i|}},$$

With $x \in [-100, 100]^2$

- **Hansen** function. The function is given by the following:

$$f(x) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^5 (i \cos((i+1)x_1 + i))\right) * \left(\sum_{j=1}^5 (j \cos((j+1)x_2 + j))\right)$$

With $x \in [-10, 10]^2$

- **HARTMAN3** function. The function is given by the following:

$$f(x) = - \sum_{i=1}^4 c_i \exp\left(- \sum_{j=1}^3 a_{ij} (x_j - p_{ij})^2\right),$$

Where $a = a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 10 & 30 \\ 0.1 & 10 & 35 \\ 3 & 10 & 30 \\ 0.1 & 10 & 35 \end{bmatrix}$, $c = c_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0 \\ 1.2 \\ 3.0 \\ 3.2 \end{bmatrix}$, $P = p_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3689 & 0.1170 & 0.2673 \\ 0.4699 & 0.4387 & 0.7470 \\ 0.1091 & 0.8732 & 0.5547 \\ 0.03815 & 0.5743 & 0.8828 \end{bmatrix}$

With $x \in [0, 1]^3$

- **HARTMAN6** function. The function is given by the following:

$$f(x) = - \sum_{i=1}^4 c_i \exp\left(- \sum_{j=1}^6 a_{ij} (x_j - p_{ij})^2\right),$$

$$\text{Where } a = a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 10 & 3 & 17 & 3.5 & 1.7 & 8 \\ 0.05 & 10 & 17 & 0.1 & 8 & 14 \\ 3 & 3.5 & 1.7 & 10 & 17 & 8 \\ 17 & 8 & 0.05 & 10 & 0.1 & 14 \end{bmatrix}, c = c_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0 \\ 1.2 \\ 3.0 \\ 3.2 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$P = p_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1312 & 0.1696 & 0.5569 & 0.0124 & 0.8283 & 0.5886 \\ 0.2329 & 0.4135 & 0.8307 & 0.3736 & 0.1004 & 0.9991 \\ 0.2348 & 0.1451 & 0.3522 & 0.2883 & 0.3047 & 0.6650 \\ 0.4047 & 0.8828 & 0.8723 & 0.5743 & 0.1091 & 0.0381 \end{bmatrix}$$

With $x \in [0, 1]^6$

- **POTENTIAL** function. As a test case, the molecular conformation corresponding to the global minimum of the energy of N atoms interacting via the Lennard–Jones potential [37] is utilized. The function to be minimized is defined as follows:

$$V_{LJ}(r) = 4\epsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^6 \right],$$

In the current experiments, two different cases were studied: N = 3, 4.

- **SHEKEL5** function:

$$f(x) = - \sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{1}{(x - a_i) (x - a_i)^T + c_i}$$

$$\text{Where } a = \begin{bmatrix} 4 & 4 & 4 & 4 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 8 & 8 & 8 & 8 \\ 6 & 6 & 6 & 6 \\ 3 & 7 & 3 & 7 \end{bmatrix}, c = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0.2 \\ 0.2 \\ 0.4 \\ 0.4 \end{bmatrix},$$

With $x \in [0, 10]^4$

- **SHEKEL7** function:

$$f(x) = - \sum_{i=1}^7 \frac{1}{(x - a_i) (x - a_i)^T + c_i}$$

$$\text{Where } a = \begin{bmatrix} 4 & 4 & 4 & 4 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 8 & 8 & 8 & 8 \\ 6 & 6 & 6 & 6 \\ 3 & 7 & 3 & 7 \\ 2 & 9 & 2 & 9 \\ 5 & 3 & 5 & 3 \end{bmatrix}, c = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0.2 \\ 0.2 \\ 0.4 \\ 0.4 \\ 0.6 \\ 0.3 \end{bmatrix},$$

With $x \in [0, 10]^4$

- **SHEKEL10** function:

$$f(x) = - \sum_{i=1}^{10} \frac{1}{(x - a_i) (x - a_i)^T + c_i}$$

Where $a = \begin{bmatrix} 4 & 4 & 4 & 4 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 8 & 8 & 8 & 8 \\ 6 & 6 & 6 & 6 \\ 3 & 7 & 3 & 7 \\ 2 & 9 & 2 & 9 \\ 5 & 5 & 3 & 3 \\ 8 & 1 & 8 & 1 \\ 6 & 2 & 6 & 2 \\ 7 & 3.6 & 7 & 3.6 \end{bmatrix}$, $c = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0.2 \\ 0.2 \\ 0.4 \\ 0.4 \\ 0.6 \\ 0.3 \\ 0.7 \\ 0.5 \\ 0.6 \end{bmatrix}$,

With $x \in [0, 10]^4$

- **SINUSOIDAL** function

$$f(x) = -(2.5 \prod_{i=1}^n \sin(x_i - z) + \prod_{i=1}^n \sin(5(x_i - z))), \quad 0 \leq x_i \leq \pi.$$

The experiments use $n = 16$, and $z = \frac{\pi}{6}$ and the corresponding function denoted by the label SINU16.

- **RASTRIGIN** function. The function is given by the following:

$$f(x) = x_1^2 + x_2^2 - \cos(18x_1) - \cos(18x_2),$$

With $x \in [-1, 1]^2$

- **ROSENBROCK** function. The function is given by the following:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (100(x_{i+1} - x_i^2)^2 + (x_i - 1)^2),$$

At range $-30 \leq x_i \leq 30$, in the experiments using function with $n = 16$.

- **Test2N** function. This function is given by the equation:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^4 x_i^4 - 16x_i^2 + 5x_i, \quad x_i \in [-5, 5]$$

The function has 2^n in the specified range and in the experiments $n = 4, 5, 6$.

- **Test30N** function. This function is given by:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{10} \sin^2(3\pi x_1) * \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} ((x_i - 1)^2(1 + \sin^2(3\pi x_{i+1}))) + (x_n - 1)^2(1 + \sin^2(2\pi x_n))$$

$x_i \in [-10,10]$, The function has 30^n local minima in the search space and in the experiments $n = 3, 4$.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To compare various differential evolution methods for global optimization, certain parameters were kept constant. The parallel implementation of differential evolution was employed in these comparative experiments. The performance of the proposed PDE algorithm was assessed through a series of experiments utilizing 10 parallel units. The existing OpenMP library [38] facilitated the parallelization, and the entire technique was implemented using the C++ programming language. All experiments were conducted on a system equipped with an Intel (R) Core (TM) i7-8650U multi-core processor and 16 GB of RAM, using (the Windows 11 Pro) operating system, and the experimental settings used in the proposed PDE method are presented in Table 1. The effect of the proposed PDE is shown graphically in Figure 3, where the function calls for the functions SHEKEL5, SHEKEL7, and SHEKEL10 using the four schemes of differential weights are plotted. The population size for all consists of 10 particles. To ensure the reliability and validity of the research, experiments were conducted 30 times and concerned Tables 2. In Table 2, the columns display the average number of function calls for each problem, with the last row indicating the total number of function calls. The fraction in parentheses represents the proportion of runs in which the global optimum was found; if this number is absent, it signifies that the global minimum was identified in every independent run (100% success rate). The column labeled STATIC refers to a fixed differential weight value ($F = 0.8$), while the columns Ali and MDE present results from experiments of Ali, M. Montaz and Charilogis, V.; Tsoulos, I.G, respectively conducted in [36]. The column for the proposed PDE corresponds to the proposed Parallel Differential Evolution algorithm that utilizes a (1-to-1) propagation scheme with 10 threads.

Table 1: The following settings were initially used to conduct the experiments

Parameter	Value	Explanation
NP	10	Number of populations (agents)
propagation	1-to-1	scenario
N_R	5	iterations
N_I	2	islands
M	30	Number of iterations
ϵ	10^{-4}	Small positive number

The values of the global minimum for all tested benchmark functions resulting from experiments in Tables 2 and 3 are depicted in Figures 3 and 4, respectively. The plot of Figure 3 reveals the superiority of the proposed PDE method, but STATIC, Ali, and MDE

methods show a higher number of function calls in all problems. Note that the proposed PDE algorithm proves its proficiency by getting an identical global minimum at (1, 1) with a value of zero for the ROSENBROCK function compared with the modified MDE that gets the global minimum at (0, 0).

Table 2: Statistical Comparison of Function Calls across Different Differential Evolution Optimization Methods and PDE Using a (1-to-1) Propagation Scheme with 10 Threads

NO	PROBLEMS	Static	Ali	MDE	Proposed PDE
1	BF1 (Bohachevsky)	996	1124	889	300
2	BF2 (Bohachevsky)	926	1026	816	300
3	BRANIN	878	900	730	300
4	CM4 (Cosine Mixture)	1148(0.70)	1991	1103	610
5	Camel back	1049	904(0.93)	846	610
6	Easom	447	448	446	310
7	EXP (16)	3578	7082	3521	300
8	EXP (32)	7082	14125	7022	300
9	GOLDSTEIN and PRICE	945	993	915	300
10	GRIEWANK	947	921	826	300
11	Hansen	2104	1949	1479	310

Continued Table 2 Statistical Comparison of Function Calls Across Different Differential Evolution Optimization Methods and PDE Using a (1-to-1) Propagation Scheme with 10 Threads

NO	PROBLEMS	Static	Ali	MDE	Proposed PDE
12	HARTMAN3	1017	1005	952	310
13	HARTMAN6	4679(0.90)	3744(0.97)	3128(0.87)	610
14	Potential 3	21473	2284	8197	300
15	Potential 4	44191(0.43)	3098 (0.33)	24659(0.97)	300
16	RASTRIGIN	841	994	777	300
17	ROSENBROCK (16)	160349	160538(0.60)	38315	300
18	SHEKEL5	4389(0.97)	4266	2839(0.83)	1500
19	SHEKEL7	3905	3685	2668	2100
20	SHEKEL10	4049	3548	2629	2400
21	SINUSOIDAL (16)	6892	3628(0.97)	16905	3000
22	Test function 2N4	2785	2275	2221	300
23	Test function 2N5	4481	3170	3122	3000
24	Test function 2N6	6852	4286	4296	3000
25	Test function 30N3	1033	1098	951	610
26	Test function 30N4	1355	1444	1285	610
-	TOTAL	288394	230529(0.8)	131539(0.67)	22580
-	TOTAL without ROSENBROCK (16)	128045	69991(0.2)	93224(0.67)	22280

Figure 3: The effect of the usage of the proposed PDE algorithm versus different differential evolution optimization methods

Table 3: The values of the global minimum for test functions by the proposed (PDE) algorithm are approximately the same accuracy as the modified differential evolution (MDE)

NO	PROBLEMS	MDE	Proposed PDE
1	BF1(Bohachevsky)	0.0	0.0
2	BF2(Bohachevsky)	0.0	0.0
3	BRANIN	0.397887	0.397887
4	CM4(Cosine Mixture)	-	Global max 0.4
5	Camel	-	- 1.0316
6	Easom	- 1.0	- 1.0
7	EXP (16)	- 1.0	- 1.0
8	EXP (32)	- 1.0	- 1.0
9	GOLDSTEIN	3.0	3.0
10	GRIEWANK	0.0	0.0
11	Hansen	-176.54	-176.54
12	HARTMAN3	-3.86	-3.86
13	HARTMAN6	-3.322	-3.321
14	Potential 3	0	0
15	Potential 4	0	0
16	RASTRIGIN	- 2.0	- 2.0
17	ROSENBROCK (16)	0.0 at (0,0)	0.0 at (1,1) better
18	SHEKEL5	- 10.10	- 10.09
19	SHEKEL7	- 10.34	- 10.34
20	SHEKEL10	- 10.53	- 10.52
21	SINUSOIDAL16	- 3.5	- 3.5
22	Test function 2N4	-156.6646	-156.665
23	Test function 2N5	-195.8308	-195.831
24	Test function 2N6	-234.9969	-234.997
25	Test function 30N3	0	0
26	Test function 30N4	0	0

Figure 4: Comparison of total function calls of benchmark tested functions without ROSENBROCK function using different differential evolution optimization methods

Table 4 provides further insights, presenting computational times, additionally; the comparisons reveal a reduction in execution time, as illustrated in Figure 5, alongside a decrease in the time needed to attain the global minimum values for the functions.

Table 4: Time comparisons (seconds) when applying the proposed PDE and different differential evolution optimization methods to test functions

NO	PROBLEMS	MTDE	MDE	Proposed PDE
1	POTENTIAL 4	1.42	0.812	0.0966
2	POTENTIAL 3	0.585	0.218	0.0654
3	EXP (32)	0.425	0.412	0.320
4	EXP (16)	0.131	0.135	0.039
5	SINU (16)	0.338	0.768	0.187

Figure 5: Comparison of executing time applying the proposed PDE and different differential evolution optimization methods to some of the test functions

5. CONCLUSION

By harnessing parallel processing capabilities, experiments can drastically reduce computational time and enhance the efficiency of the optimization process. However, parallelizing differential evolution necessitates meticulous consideration of several factors, such as load balancing, exploration-exploitation trade-offs, and communication overhead. Parallel implementations of DE present a compelling approach for accelerating optimization tasks and addressing intricate problems. The proposed technique operates within parallel computing environments, employing the differential evolution algorithm to establish independent populations across parallel computing units. These units partition the initial population of agents, periodically exchanging the best objective function values via a (1-to-1) propagation technique, where randomly selected subpopulations share information. Furthermore, even a subset of the computing units can efficiently determine when to terminate the method. The experimental results confirmed that the proposed technique effectively identified the global minimum across various problems from the related literature. Generally, while the parallel processing units increased, the number of required function calls and the time needed for the optimization process decreased. This indicates that the proposed PDE algorithm is more efficient in exploring the search space of the test functions, leading to greater accuracy and reduced time in achieving the global minimum.

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